

Gender-Based Violence In Light Of The Coronavirus Pandemic: A Descriptive Study On Jordanian Women

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 29, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Family violence, Corona effects, Women, Man violence, Gender</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5137880</p>	<p><i>The objective of this study is to provide descriptive statistics on the percentages, causes, forms and sources of battered women in Jordan. The study was conducted on the basis of the social survey method and the electronic questionnaire instrument for intentional samples of (1308) Jordanian women. Results showed that in the Corona pandemic in 2020, 17.1% of the sample examined were abused. And husbands are more violently engaging 37.5% against their wives, followed by 28.6% for fathers to daughters and 26.8% for brothers against sisters. The results indicates that the causes of this violence related to social factors such as patriarchy, intervention of family and relatives, and economic factors such as high living costs, poor household income, and poverty. It also concluded that verbal, physical, and psychological violence are the most common types of violence. Women in southern Jordan, the poorest and least educated, and those living in large households were found to be the most abused, according to the survey.</i></p>

Introduction

Violence against women is a global concern (Zahrani 2010). Most international studies confirm an increase in the volume of violence against women. (Petermon et al., 2020), in several contemporary societies, to reach 30% (World Health Organization, 2021), particularly during of the Corona epidemic. The phenomenon varies according to several civilizational, cultural, religious, economic and social factors, which result in forms of violence against women, such as anger, restriction, coercion, forbidden, expulsion, beating, threat, and killing. Based on this, many cases of violence against women are inseparable from the various changes that our societies have recently undergone (Khatibeh, 2018).

It is also linked to cultural and traditional standers that make "outside family" relations, especially sexual relations forbidden, and even consider them a "shameful disgrace" (Carron, 2020), even classified as crimes affecting the family in the Arab culture, as everyone reveres the customary value of "family honor" and it is linked to a woman's purity and sexual chastity (Dodd, 2009). Surprisingly, in 2020 (17) murders against women were recorded in Jordan.

The Study Problem

This study reveals the rates of violence against women, causes, forms and sources in during the Covid -19 pandemic. Violence constitutes a dangerous phenomenon and indicates an unacceptable aggressive behavior that has negative effects on the health of women, the family and society together. Therefore, describing the facts of violence against women represents the depth of the study's problem.

The study gains importance from the fact that it provides data on a dangerous phenomenon that is harmful to women's, people's and society's health as a whole. It also provides objective data on various dimensions of violence against women in Jordan, which constitutes a need for local, international and human knowledge useful for governments, society's institutions, social workers and researchers to confront this type of violence against women.

Study objectives and questions:

The study aims to provide data related to the rates of violence against women in Jordan, sources and causes, in light of the Corona pandemic. Therefore, the study answers the following questions:

1. Did the Corona pandemic affect the increase in violence against women in Jordan? What are the actual rates of violence against women in Jordan?
2. What are the causes of violence against women in Jordan in light of the Corona pandemic?
3. What are the forms and sources of violence against women in Jordan in related to Corona pandemic?

Violence is defined in the dictionary of social sciences as: "The use of restraint or violence in an illegal or inconsistent manner with the law that affects an individual's will." (Badawi, 1986, p. 125). The Universal Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women, signed by the United Nations in 1993, defines violence: "Any act of violence based on gender that results in or is likely to result in physical, sexual or

psychological harm or suffering to a woman, including threats to commit such an act, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of freedom, whether it occurs in public or private life” (Al-Gawasmah, 2010). This is considered an attack on her human dignity, an abuse of her existence and a weakening of her position (Al-Majali, 2018), and this makes women less adaptive and closer to social and psychological isolation, more feeling of inferiority, fear, symptoms of anxiety and depression, less productive and emotional instability (Al-Ibrahim, 2010).

Study methodology (method and procedures):

The study relies on the social survey method to provide data on violence against women in during the Corona pandemic, this approach is suitable for determining the characteristics of the phenomenon and describing its nature and various dimensions. The study population consists of all Jordanian women over the age of 18 years, and a purposive sample of (1,308) was selected from various governorates of Jordan. By relying on the electronic questionnaire tool as a main tool for collecting data, the researcher design this tool to achieve the goals and objectives of the study. The validity and stability were verified, and the data was entered into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program, and descriptive statistics were used, such as frequencies and percentages, to indicate the characteristics of the sample, and the percentages of violence against women, causes, forms and sources in during the Corona pandemic in Jordan.

The demographic characteristics of the study sample:

The number of unmarried women respondents reached (764) with a rating 58.4%, followed by (476) married women rating 36.4%, while the minority were widowed and divorced women. 51.9% live in the central governorates, and their number is (679), followed by 41% from the northern governorates, and the rest of the respondents were from southern Jordan.

The majority were educated women holding masters degrees or higher at a rate of 74.3%, while 24.2% and other minority were of secondary education or less.

The sample was contains four age groups 820 of them aged between 18 to 26 years, and the lowest group amounted to 9.8%, whose ages ranged between 36-44 years. In regards to the monthly family income, 405 rating 38.5% did not exceeded 700 usd or less, while 11.9% were at 1400 usd or more (see chart 1).

1- Did the Corona pandemic affect the increase in violence against women in Jordan? What are the actual rates of violence against women in Jordan?

Chart 2 shows Jordanian women respondents who regarding to what extant violence against women increased in during the pandemic averaging between two levels :(high), according to (460) respondents, rating 35.2%, and (medium), according to (320) respondents, rating 24.5%. While less than 1/4 respondents indicated that it was not increasing. The rating were very similar regarding the increase in male violence against women during quarantines days, with slight variations as in chart (3).

During the full quarantine, (392) women answered, by 30%, that violence against women increased significantly. (376) responded, at rate of 28.7%, that it increased to a moderate degree, and the rest were varies.

Chart 4 data showed that the ratio of battered women in Jordan during the Corona pandemic in 2020 amounted to 17.1% (224 surveyed women out of 1,308) , which is less than most previous studies such as (Al-Majali, 2018: WHO, 2021) studies, and the rest were responded that they were not subjected to any form of violence, which explains that the outbreak of the Corona epidemic produced anxiety, fear and phobia among people and families and thus reflected on the increase in family cohesion, harmony and tolerance more than conflict and violence due to the presence of danger to everyone's life.

2- What are the causes of violence against women in Jordan in light of the Corona pandemic?

The social causes of violence against women:

Health causes related to men's violence against women:

Chart 6 data shows the most important health causes driving violence are due first, Sexual dysfunction according to (412) women, rating 31.5%, followed by muscle strength of men according to (390) respondents rating 30%, followed by illness of the husband or the man. The rest was distributed on other health reasons, such as poor hygiene or illness for women.

The economic causes of violence against women:

Chart 7 shows the most important economic causes of violence against women, represented by (675) women in difficult living pressures at a rate of 51.5%, followed by low family income, at 26.7%, followed by other reasons such as poverty.

Chart 8 shows from the women's answers that the most important psychological causes of violence against women are due to the temperament of men, according to (526) women, at a rate of 40.2%, and (420) confirmed the aggressiveness of men at a rate of 32.1%, with other reasons such as the weak personality of women and the jealousy of men and others.

4- What are the forms and sources of violence against women in Jordan in related to Corona pandemic?

Chart 9 shows the following conclusions:

- Verbal violence is the most common practice against women and is widespread in Jordan, at 62.2% (140 women out of 224).
- Physical violence, 14.3% (32 women out of 224) were subjected to this form.
- Psychological violence, 12.5% of women were exposed.
- Sexual violence, only 4 women out of 224 responded, rating 1.8%, which is a very low percentage, perhaps due to women's shyness to declare this, in addition to that the study was conducted on married and unmarried women which suggests that it did not agree with the results of local and international studies that had proven sexual violence to be the most common such as (Al-Hayassat, 2016) and (Elspeth & Mirzoev, 2021).

Chart 10 shows (84) respondents who responded that the source of violence is related to their husbands, rating 37.5%. While (64) referred it to their fathers, rating 28.6%, followed by brothers against sisters (60), at a rate of 26.8%, and the rest referred violence to their work colleagues, showing that these results contradict with Al-Majali's 2018 results.

The study included several data indicating that:

The psychological effects of violence were the most common, and there is a connection between violence and the place of residence, monthly family income, family size and level of education, based on the data that battered women in tribal and semi-tribal societies in southern Jordan regions are more subjected to violence compared to women in central and northern Jordan and the poorest and least educated, and those who live in large families suffer the most from men's violence compared to others.

Recommendations

The necessity of enlightening family and community awareness of violence crucial negative effect against women, establishing family reform offices and developing targeted programs, enacting legislation criminalizing violence and solving problems of poverty and family living conditions.

References

- Al- Ibrahim, A. (2010). Mental Health among Battered Jordanian women. *Islamic University Magazine, (Islamic Studies Series)*. 18(2), 229 – 329. Palestine.
- Al-Gawasmah, S. (2010). A study of the Status of Women in the Hebron Governorate, within the project of combating violence against Palestinian Women through empowerment of community's organizations. Meftah Publication.
- Al-Hiasat, Nadia Ibrahim (2016). The causes and forms of violence against the wife in the Jordanian society, "A field study", studies, humanities and social sciences, University of Jordan, vol. 43, p. 4. pp. 1773-1788
- Al-Majali, Samih Zaid (2018), Violence against Women in Jordanian Society, "A Field Study in Karak Governorate", Mu'tah for Research and Studies, Human and Social Sciences Series, Volume 33, Issue 1, pp. 237-288
- A-Zahrani, M. (2010). The Role of the Press in Addressing Family Violence Crimes. *Okaz Newspaper*, Analytic study from 2004 – 2008. Unpublished M.A thesis. Jordan. Al karak. Mutah University.
- Badawi, A. (1986 A.D.). *Dictionary of Social Sciences Terminology*, Library of Lebanon, Beirut.
- Barakat, Halim (2011). *Contemporary Arab Society: A sociological survey*, Center for Arab Unity Studies, Beirut.
- Carron, A, C (2020). Shame, Family Honor, and Dating Abuse: Lessons From an Exploratory Study of South Asian Muslims, Violence Against Women, Vol 26, 15, pp. 2004–2023 <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077801219895115>
- Dodd, P. (2009). Family Honor and the Forces of Change in Arab Society. *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, 4 (1), 40-54. Doi: 10.1017/S0020743800027264
- Elspeith, Z, Mirzoev, T (2021). Intimate Partner Violence against Indigenous Women in Sololá, Guatemala: Qualitative Insights into Perspectives of Service Providers, *Violence against Women*, Vol 27. P1-19 <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077801220981145>

- Khataybeh, Yousef Damen (2018), Marital Problems Threatening Family Security in Light of Some Social Variables: A Social Study on Husbands Working in Governmental Departments in Irbid Governorate. Journal of Man and Society, University of Tlemcen, No. 14. pp. 240-269
- Petermon, A, & et al (2020), A Gender Lens on Covid_19 Pandemics and Violence against Women and Children, Center for Global Development. <https://www.cgdev.org/blog/gender-lens-covid-19-pandemics-and-violence-against-women-and-children>
- World Health Organization (2021), Violence against Women, website: <https://www.who.int/ar/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/violence-against-women>

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